

An indica source of male sterile cytoplasm and its fertility restoration for hybrid rice breeding

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The search for alternate sources of sterile cytoplasm in hybrid rice breeding is a priority because more than 90% of the rice hybrids released throughout the world are based on a single sterile cytoplasm—wild abortive (WA). Because of the very narrow genetic base provided by the single cytoplasmic source, hybrids carrying this cytoplasm can become vulnerable to pests and diseases found associated with it.

We observed reciprocal differences for pollen sterility in the F_2 generation in a number of crosses. In one such cross (Pusa 743/Pusa 33), male sterile segregants were observed during 1992, whereas in another reciprocal (Pusa 33/Pusa 743) all the F_2 plants were fertile. This indicated that Pusa 743 has sterility-inducing cytoplasm. Of several breeding lines tested for fertility restoration in this cytoplasm, 30% were found to be restorers. Initially, 21% of the lines were identified as maintainers. But only 10% showed a stable reaction for sterility maintenance in the later backcross generations. This indicated that fertility restoration was governed by a single dominant gene, although a majority of the crosses showed significant deviations from Mendelian segregation because of a deficit of recessives. Japonica rices are likely to maintain sterility in this cytoplasm. Three cytoplasmic male sterile lines with a stable sterility reaction were developed. Pusa 1127A was found to be agronomically promising. ■

Male sterile lines for hybrid rice breeding

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Experience with hybrid maize indicates the utility of diverse cytoplasmic sources as a source of cytoplasmic male sterility. Crop heterogeneity is desirable for the sustainability of commercial hybrids. We studied the morphological and physiological characters of male sterile lines belonging to diverse cytoplasm. We studied eight male sterile lines belonging to wild abortive types (V20 A, Zhengshan 97 A, BO A, Jin 23 A, and Zhi A), IDR or Indonesian paddy rice type (U1 A), dwarf abortive type (Xieqinzao A), and BT or japonica type (80-4 A) during the winter season of 1993-94 in a randomized block design with three replications. Each line was planted in a single row, with a spacing of 20 × 20 cm. The crop was maintained as per recommended practices.

From a nursery 10-, 20-, and 30-d-old seedling samples were taken for study. Clean plant samples were collected from the nursery using a digging plate and the roots were freed of soil by washing them with water. From five seedlings per replication, observations were recorded on length, volume by water displacement in a burette, and weight of root and shoot portions. Total tillers, panicle-bearing tillers, and plant height at the vegetative (60 d) and flowering stages were also recorded for each test line. Pollen reaction was studied using an I-KI (1%) solution. The percentage of a certain type of pollen was calculated by the ratio of its occurrence to the total number of pollen grains in a microscopic field. Seed set on male sterile

lines was studied in isolation by bagging.

Some lines that expressed good seedling growth and vigor in the nursery were Zhi A (root length, shoot volume, and shoot weight at 30 d), Xieqinzao A (root and shoot length at 30 d, root and shoot volume at 30 d), and Jin 23 A (shoot length at three stages of sampling and shoot weight at 20 and 30 d).

Jin 23 A, Zhi A, and 80-4A were tall at the vegetative and flowering stages. The lines flowered in 85-95 d, with Jin 23 A being early and Zhengshan 97 A late to flower. The exertion of stigmas outside the floret was well expressed in BO A, Jin 23 A, U1 A, and Zhi A. Lines Jin 23 A, V20 A, and Zhengshan 97 A showed 100% unstained and irregular-shaped pollen, whereas Zhi A, BO A, and U1 A showed 99-99.5% sterile irregular pollen. Xieqinzao A had 5% stained pollen and 80-4 A had all pollen grains circular, of which 50% were stained. Line BO A had a maximum panicle-bearing tillers and was on a par with Jin 23 A, Zhi A, V 20 A, and Xieqinzao A. There was no seed set in the panicle bag. ■

Fertility-altering conditions of promising thermo-sensitive genic male sterile lines in rice

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Characterizing thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines with respect

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